

Life, Intelligence, and Cognition: The Living Triad and the Artificial Corollary

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Abstract

Contemporary research in psychology, cognitive science, and artificial intelligence tends to identify intelligence with measurable cognitive performance — an equation this paper rejects. Drawing on Aristotelian and Peircean resources, and building on the autopoietic and biosemiotic traditions, I propose a distinction between intelligence and cognition that situates both within a triadic framework of the living. Life, intelligence, and cognition are not separate items but interdependent dimensions of a single living being. On the proposed account, life is condition — the substantial standing of an individuated subject, in a determinate form and at a determinate here and now; intelligence is the *modus essendi* of that subject as a being in change, traversing the passage from potency to act; cognition is life as organisation under another description, the organised yield through which a living being coordinates with its environment. The mediating relation, with the structure of a Peircean Thirdness, is a process of change in which autopoietic self-maintenance and biosemiotic sense-making form a single integrated operation. This process — negentropy, in a stipulated philosophical-semiotic sense — converts environmental indeterminacy into meaningful order for a subject.

From this architecture follows a reformed notion of agency-as-subjectiveness, distinguishable from the symmetric agency of actor-network theory and adjacent accounts. The artificial case appears as a corollary. Contemporary AI does not reproduce life as organisation in the full autopoietic sense; it reproduces an externalised abstraction of selected higher-order cognitive capacities. The structure that results is not a defective version of the living triad but a different kind of organisation, whose form cannot be specified by subtracting sides from ours. I call this structural configuration jagged intelligence. The paper closes by drawing the implications of this redescription for the opacity of advanced artificial systems and for the problem of control.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, philosophy of biology, agency, negentropy, cognition.*

1. Introduction

Intelligence is commonly treated, in psychology, cognitive science, and artificial intelligence research, as a set of cognitive capacities measurable through performance. To this day, however, the scientific community has not converged on a shared definition of intelligence¹.

¹ See R. J. Sternberg and D. K. Detterman, eds., *What Is Intelligence? Contemporary Viewpoints on Its Nature and Definition* (Norwood, NJ: Ablex, 1986); S. Legg and M. Hutter, "A Collection of Definitions of Intelligence", in *Advances*

This equation between intelligence and cognition — the identification of the first with what the second produces — has roots in early twentieth-century psychometrics. Early psychometric approaches identified intelligence with selected capacities that could be operationalised, measured, and compared across individuals. Later theories differed over whether intelligence should be understood psychometrically, computationally, biologically, or neurocognitively. Yet many retained a common assumption: intelligence is to be explained through cognitive organisation and assessed through performance.

To model intelligence as a faculty, and cognition as the process that produces it, is to externalise both: it is to define them independently of the subject, who is in turn reduced to a substrate on which faculties are exercised and processes run. This externalisation is precisely what has made it possible to call the activity of artificial agents a kind of *intelligence* — artificial intelligence — and so to set up a comparative terrain on which living and non-living beings can be ranked by their performance. The reductive move at work here goes one step further than its proponents typically acknowledge: by setting aside the individual dimension of the living, it reifies every expression of a living being into an output to be compared with other outputs.

If we are to understand why natural intelligence and artificial intelligence are different — and in what sense they are — without falling back on appeals to differences of substrate, we need to reconsider the subject. This paper rejects the equation of intelligence with cognitive performance by drawing on and putting to work a distinction between intelligence and cognition. The argument that follows is situated at the intersection of philosophy of biology, philosophy of cognition, and theory of artificial intelligence, and intervenes on three connected problems: the operational definition of intelligence in the cognitive sciences and in AI research; the question of which level of description carries the explanatory burden in accounts of the living; and the conditions under which a model of the living can, or cannot, be transferred to an artefact.

In the framework I shall develop, life, intelligence, and cognition are not separate items to be inventoried but intertwined dimensions of a single living being, and may be represented as a triad whose three sides represent different but complementary aspects of it.

The first side, joining life and intelligence, is *ontological*: it presents the fundamental dimension of the living, where life is *condition* — *ousia*, the substantial standing of the living subject as an

in *Artificial General Intelligence: Concepts, Architectures and Algorithms*, ed. B. Goertzel and P. Wang (Amsterdam: IOS Press, 2007), 17–24, Da Silveira, et al. “Intelligence across Humans and Machines: A Joint Perspective.” *Frontiers in Psychology* 14 (2023): 1209761.

individuated being whose mode of being is to be alive² — and intelligence is the *modus essendi* of such a being, the mode of being as a *changing being* that stands in the transformative passage between potency and act. That mode of being is the passage from *dynamis* to *energeia* through the interpretation of its environment.

Consequently, the second side, joining intelligence and cognition, is the *process of change* that the living being embodies as intelligent: at once adaptive and interpretive of its environment, and yielding the living being's self-organisation.

The third side, connecting cognition and life, is the *epistemological and procedural* face of the living being — the dimension in which both pre-reflective and reflective capacities, modellable as cognitive, are realised.

On this framework, the reductive equation of intelligence with cognitive performance is a category error: it mistakes the organised outcome of one side of the triad for the modality of being expressed in another, and so collapses the ontological dimension of the living into its describable, epistemological face. Cognition, for what follows, is the organised yield of a living system, the stabilisable and describable domain through which it regulates and configures its coping with an environment; intelligence is the *modus essendi* of the same system, the *changing being* whose passage from potency to act is what such organisation expresses and sustains.

The framework “life, intelligence, cognition” entails an ontology, but it is not vitalist: it introduces no second substance and no animating force, and it does not treat the living being as exempt from physical description. It claims only that living existence is not exhausted by, nor eliminable in favour of, an organisational description given from without. Organisation is necessary for the persistence of a living being, but it is not sufficient to account for aliveness as such. It specifies how the living condition is maintained through time; it does not by itself establish that there is a living subject whose condition is being maintained.

From this architecture, a reformed notion of agency follows directly. If intelligence is the *changing being* — the *modus essendi* of a finite subject in the passage from potency to act — then agency is interactionally asymmetric: it belongs to a being that defines its own individuality and regulates its activity according to what its continued existence requires.

The artificial case then appears as a corollary, rather than a counter-example.

An artificial system can reproduce only a narrowed externalised abstraction of cognitive capacities drawn from one side of the triad, without the conditional and interpretive relations that, in the living,

²*Ousia* is used here in the categorial sense — Aristotle, *Categories* 2a11–16, on primary *ousia* as the individuated particular that is neither said of nor in a subject. The connection of soul, life, and substantial being for the living individual is registered, without entering the *De Anima*, in *Metaphysics* Z.10 (1035b14–15) and Z.11 (1037a5).

give it sense. What structure such a system thereby forms is, I shall argue, not a deficient version of the living triad but a different kind of organisation, one whose form cannot be specified simply by subtracting life and interpretation from the living case: not our triangle with two sides missing, but possibly another figure altogether. This recasts the much-discussed opacity of advanced systems as a limit in principle — a reframing whose stakes for the control of such systems I take up in Section 6. The argument proceeds as follows.

Section 2 distinguishes life as condition from life as organisation and uses this distinction to separate intelligence from cognition. Section 3 develops the mediating process through which living beings convert environmental indeterminacy into organised sense-making. Section 4 presents the triadic architecture and defines intelligence as the mode of being of the living subject in change. Section 5 derives a corresponding account of agency-as-subjectiveness and contrasts it with symmetrical accounts of agency as causal participation. Section 6 applies the framework to artificial systems, arguing that contemporary AI reproduces an externalised abstraction of cognitive capacities rather than the intelligence of a living subject.

2. Life as Condition and Life as Organisation

I begin by fixing the premise on which the argument rests. To clarify the distinction between intelligence and cognition in living beings, I first distinguish two registers of life: organisation and condition. They provide the spine of what I call, throughout this paper, the “life, intelligence, cognition” framework. The present section establishes the first two of its three terms; the third, cognition, and the relations among all three, will be developed in what follows.

By *life as organisation*, I mean the processes, mechanisms, and regularities through which a living being maintains itself, regulates its exchanges with an environment, and preserves its viability over time. This is the dimension addressed by Maturana and Varela’s autopoietic theory³; by Di Paolo’s supplementation of autopoiesis with adaptivity, the organism’s capacity to regulate itself with respect to its own conditions of viability; and by Moreno and Mossio’s account of biological autonomy as a regime of mutually dependent constraints that collectively maintain the very constraints that produce them⁴. What these accounts share is that they describe the living *from without*: they specify organisation that can be modelled, abstracted, and, within limits, compared across systems.

By *life as condition*, by contrast, I mean aliveness as such: the ontological fact that there is an individuated, embodied subject for which its own continuation and interruption can matter.

³ H. R. Maturana and F. J. Varela, *Autopoiesis and Cognition: The Realization of the Living* (Dordrecht: Reidel, 1980).

⁴ E. A. Di Paolo, “Autopoiesis, Adaptivity, Teleology, Agency”, *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences* 4 (2005): 429–452; A. Moreno and M. Mossio, *Biological Autonomy: A Philosophical and Theoretical Enquiry* (Dordrecht: Springer, 2015).

Two complementary vocabularies help fix this notion. In Aristotelian terms, the condition is the *ousia* of the living, taken in the categorial sense — the substantial standing of the individuated living particular, the *that-it-is* of the subject. Life as condition is therefore the bare condition of aliveness: life as it is, before any organisational description of what it does⁵.

Both registers of life — the condition and the organisation — share two constraints, which the framework will treat as constitutive of what it is for a being to be living. The first is structure: the determinate physical form in which the living individual is realised, the specific composition that makes a living being this living being rather than some other. The second is contingency: the location of the living individual at a particular here and now, the spatio-temporal window within which its existence unfolds. These two constraints are not external limits imposed on an otherwise unbounded life; they are what condition and organisation are constrained by, and what they answer to. The condition is the standing of an individuated subject in a determinate form, here and now; the organisation is the regime by which that standing is sustained, by that subject, in that form, in that here and now. Neither makes sense without the two.

The point against which this distinction is sustained is at once phenomenological and conceptual. A complete description of self-maintenance, adaptivity, and constraint closure characterises the living from without; whether there is a subject whose organisation it is, remains a separate question. Aliveness as such — recognised before any theory of life is offered for it, and presupposed by every description of what a living being does — is the name for what such procedural description leaves undecided.

Hans Jonas's philosophical biology reads this aliveness as the ontological structure of a being whose existence is at stake in its activity, the needful freedom by which a living individual continually wins itself against the always-imminent possibility of non-being⁶. The condition is therefore the substantial fact of a living subject in a determinate form, at a determinate here and now; the organisation is the regime by which that fact is sustained through time. Organisation specifies how aliveness is maintained; condition names the fact that aliveness is the case. That the procedural register has not produced an agreed account of what makes life arise quietly registers this difference — the limit of what such description, by its nature, can settle.

⁵ On the categorial sense of *ousia* as primary *ousia* (the individuated particular), see note 1 of the Introduction, citing Aristotle, *Categories* 2a11–16.

⁶ H. Jonas, *The Phenomenon of Life: Toward a Philosophical Biology* (New York: Harper & Row, 1966); see also A. Weber and F. J. Varela, "Life after Kant: Natural Purposes and the Autopoietic Foundations of Biological Individuality", *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences* 1 (2002): 97–125, on Jonas's role in connecting phenomenological biology to autopoietic and enactive accounts. For a different, pre-individual reading of immanence as life, see G. Deleuze, *Pure Immanence: Essays on A Life*, trans. A. Boyman (New York: Zone Books, 2001).

In the broadly Peircean terms I shall adopt throughout, the same condition of aliveness has the character of Firstness: the qualitative being-in-itself of the subject, prior to relation, marked by an irreducible indeterminacy rather than by fixed determination.

As Hoffmeyer argues, taking up Prigogine and Stengers's *order out of chaos*, the living produces order *out of indeterminacy* — an indeterminacy that runs through the organism itself⁷. The subject that relates to an indeterminate world is not a determinate mechanism confronting noise; it is itself a locus of indeterminacy, and it is precisely this that makes it capable of genuine sense-making rather than mere outputs.

Here, the focus on indeterminacy is crucial: a living being is constitutively precarious, or not fully in equilibrium, and its precariousness consists in its exposure to an environment that is itself indeterminate — indeterminate because, at the physical level, it is entropic.

The relation between the living being and this indeterminate, entropic surround is, in Peircean terms, a Secondness: the brute encounter, resistance, and exposure through which the environment is met as something other, and through which the living being is first constituted as a *semiotic* being — a being for which the surround is not merely undergone but must be encountered. The semiotic being is a subject, in the minimal sense of distinguishing itself as itself in relation to otherness.

Thompson's characterisation of living as sense-making under precarious conditions names the same fact from the side of the subject⁸: the standpoint whose existence the mechanisms of organisation presuppose but do not themselves supply.

The connection between indeterminacy and entropy at issue here covers two complementary registers, both relevant to the living. The first is thermodynamic: the environment's indeterminacy, as it presents itself to a living being, is the indeterminacy of a physical system whose configurations are governed by the second law — disorder, in the sense of an unconstrained distribution of physical states, the living being must work to render compatible with its own persistence. The second is informational: the environment is also a source of novelty and otherness with respect to what the living being already procedurally “knows” of it — a margin of what is not yet encoded, not yet integrated into the organism's regime of self-production. The term “entropy”, in what follows, is taken in this dual sense: the physical disorder against which self-production is exercised, and the informational novelty against which sense-making is exercised. It is not used as a free-floating metaphor for disorder, nor reduced

⁷ J. Hoffmeyer, *Biosemiotics: An Examination into the Signs of Life and the Life of Signs* (Scranton: University of Scranton Press, 2008); I. Prigogine and I. Stengers, *Order Out of Chaos: Man's New Dialogue with Nature* (London: Heinemann, 1984).

⁸ E. Thompson, *Mind in Life: Biology, Phenomenology, and the Sciences of Mind* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2007): 89-218.

to the technical Shannon measure of informational uncertainty in the abstract; what matters is that, in both registers, the indeterminacy is the condition to which the living being is constitutively exposed. On this basis, the two target concepts can be placed, and the asymmetry that the Peircean ordering already suggests becomes precise. Cognition, in the sense relevant to this argument, is life as organisation under another description: the same autopoietic regime, considered now in its organised yield — the stabilisable patterns of a living system's coordination with its environment, describable and comparable across systems. This is the identification Maturana and Varela proposed when they wrote that “living systems are cognitive systems, and living as a process is a process of cognition”⁹. Intelligence, by contrast, is not identifiable with life as condition. It is the *modus essendi* of such a condition — its mode of being given as a changing being — and so stands to it as an attribute stands to the *esse* it qualifies. The asymmetry between the two concept-pairs, therefore, mirrors a deeper asymmetry between the relations they answer to. Cognition collapses into the side it describes; intelligence does not, because intelligence is the modus of life, not another name for life itself.

The condition under which a subject is alive is never given apart from some organised way of regulating its relation to an environment, and intelligence — the *modus* under which that condition is the being-in-change of a subject — exists only through such organisation. But organised performance, however sophisticated, does not by itself establish that there is a subject for which its own viability is at stake, and therefore does not entail that the organisation is the organisation of an *ousia* whose mode of being is to be intelligent. This asymmetry is what blocks the reductive inference — from the presence of organised, comparable performance to the presence of intelligence — that the equation of intelligence with cognitive ability silently licenses. The distinction between condition and organisation is analytic, rather than separative: condition and organisation are inseparable in any actual living being, since there is no aliveness not maintained through some organised form of self-production, and yet no organisational form suffices to establish aliveness. Distinguishing them marks only what each one settles. Organisation settles *how* the living condition is sustained and persevered through time; it does not settle *that* there is a living subject for whom such sustaining stands for its condition of aliveness.

One clarification forestalls a predictable misreading. The difference between life as condition and life as organisation is categorial: the indeterminacy noted above belongs to the subject's substantial nature, not to a domain inaccessible to description. The distinction is between two registers, not between the known and the unknowable.

⁹ Humberto R. Maturana, "Biology of Cognition" (1970), in Humberto R. Maturana e Francisco J. Varela, *Autopoiesis and Cognition: The Realization of the Living* (Dordrecht: D. Reidel Publishing Company, 1980), 13.

It is precisely this inseparability that the static pairing of condition and organisation does not by itself articulate. Saying that the organisation perpetuates the condition, and that the condition is realised only through the organisation, asserts a relation. It does not, however, specify what kind of relation that is. That relation, which the Peircean ordering already anticipates as a Thirdness mediating Firstness and Secondness, is the topic of the next section.

3. The Process of Change: Thirdness and Negentropy

The previous section left aside the passage by which a subject's aliveness becomes the organised engagement that cognition describes. I shall argue that this passage is a process of change with the structure of a Peircean Thirdness, and that its work is the production of negentropy. By negentropy I shall mean the production and maintenance of order by a living subject: order that is thermodynamically grounded but semiotically oriented, arising through, and for the sake of, the subject's interpretive relation to its environment. This is neither the strict thermodynamic quantity introduced by Schrödinger and formalised by Brillouin¹⁰ nor a loose metaphor for orderliness, but a stipulated philosophical-semiotic concept, constrained by — but not reducible to — its thermodynamic ancestor; what follows specifies the constraint and marks the irreducibility, without claiming for the term the status of a measurable physical quantity.

Deacon's nested hierarchy of dynamical regimes supplies the needed discrimination¹¹. He distinguishes three regimes of order-production: the homeodynamic, the thermodynamic tendency by which differences are dissipated towards equilibrium; the morphodynamic, in which order emerges spontaneously from the interaction of thermodynamic processes — the level of self-organisation, whose standard instances are precisely convection cells, whirlpools, and snow crystals; and the teleodynamic, in which organisation becomes end-directed, employing homeodynamic and morphodynamic processes in the service of a self that maintains, repairs, and reproduces itself. Negentropy, in my sense, belongs only at the teleodynamic level — the level at which order-production has a subject as its referent. A cooling stone, too, reduces its local entropy through exchange with its surroundings; but nothing in that order is for the stone, and nothing in it is at stake. On the present account, the living being is the referent of its own order-production: it refers the order it creates to itself, here and now, as functional to its own persistence, in both adaptive and interpretive terms. The result is an order that has meaning — an order in which environmental difference is not merely undergone as a physical gradient but converted into a difference that matters for a subject.

¹⁰ E. Schrödinger, *What Is Life? The Physical Aspect of the Living Cell* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1944); L. Brillouin, *Science and Information Theory* (New York: Academic Press, 1956). The term *negentropy* derives from Schrödinger's "negative entropy" and is formalised by Brillouin as bound information.

¹¹ T. W. Deacon, *Incomplete Nature: How Mind Emerged from Matter* (New York: W. W. Norton, 2011): 206-325.

Having adopted Deacon's three-level distinction for the discrimination it provides, I must mark where I part from him, since the divergence bears directly on the premise of Section 2.

Deacon's project is a physicalist one: teleodynamics, and selfhood, function, and meaning with it, are to be *derived* from morphodynamic processes in a bottom-up emergence that begins with the second law and ends with the mind. On my account, the teleodynamic regime correctly characterises the *organisational* face of the living — life as organisation, the describable signature of self-maintenance in the service of a subject — but it does not constitute, exhaust, or generate the living *condition*. The condition is the standpoint that teleodynamic organisation expresses; it is not derived from thermodynamics. To use Deacon's hierarchy as a complete metaphysics of the living would be to reinstate exactly the reduction of condition to organisation in life that the premise denies. I take the hierarchy, then, as a precise description of the gradient from dissipation to self-relative order, and leave to one side its eliminative ambition.

A clarification on the second law: the living does not abolish or locally reverse it. It is thermodynamically open, and pays its entropic costs in full, exporting disorder to its surroundings in every act of self-maintenance and interpretation. The semiotic does not suspend the physical processes by which the living subject sustains itself; it directs them. What distinguishes the living subject is that the order it sustains is organised around, and answerable to, the meaning its environment has *for it*. In living beings, negentropy is, on the account I am defending, thermodynamic order-production under semiotic governance.

What yields it is a third, mediating term: the interpretive process by which the encounter with an entropic environment (Secondness) is integrated into the subject's self-maintenance — converted from mere environmental difference into significant difference, a sign to which the subject's organisation responds. This mediation, as Thirdness, is at once autopoietic and semiotic: autopoietic in that it is the self-producing regime through which the organism holds itself together, semiotic in that, as Hoffmeyer's biosemiotics insists¹², the holding-together proceeds by the interpretation of signs¹³.

One qualification is needed here. To say that the process is interpretive is not to place interpretation at the level of every lawful physical operation within the organism. Protein folding, metabolic reactions, and other constrained biochemical processes may be indispensable for semiosis without themselves amounting to full triadic interpretation. The claim is instead an integrative one. Local

¹² J. Hoffmeyer, *Biosemiotics: An Examination into the Signs of Life and the Life of Signs* (Scranton: University of Scranton Press, 2008); see also Section 2.

¹³ On this point, see H. H. Pattee, "Symbol Grounding Precedes Interpretation," *Biosemiotics* 14 (2021), and Deacon's reply in *Biosemiotics* 16, no. 1 (2023). I accept Pattee's caution that interpretation should not be located at the level of lawful biochemical processes such as protein folding, but distinguish this from the integrative level at which semantic closure becomes operative.

subsystems may function as constrained interpretants of the inputs to which they are procedurally adequate; full Thirdness, however, arises only at the level of the living subject as an organised whole, where operational, organisational, and semantic closures are jointly operative. The combination of these three closures responds to a long-standing observation within biosemiotics — notably by Barbieri¹⁴ — that operational closure as theorised in autopoietic terms is not itself a form of semantic closure, and that conflating the two loses the genuinely interpretive register that distinguishes the living.

What organises this integrative level is what, drawing on Aristotelian and biosemiotic resources, I have elsewhere called directedness: the for-the-sake-of-which under which the activity of the living subject as a whole acquires meaning, and from which each component operation takes on sense by its place in that integrated activity. Directedness and interpretation, on this account, are co-extensive but not identical. Directedness names the finalistic orientation of the subject's activity toward its own continued existence through a negentropic tendency; interpretation names the meaning that such orientation makes possible — partially, at the level of organised subsystems, and fully, at the level of the subject as an integrated whole.

Along this side — running, in the framework's terms, from intelligence to cognition — the living subject does the work by which its condition becomes its organisation.

A single illustration, drawn from a scale very different from the cellular, shows that the point is not parochial to one level of life. In the evolutionary passage of the Clitellata worms, from marine to terrestrial habit, a lineage underwent a radical transformation of its conditions of viability — osmotic, respiratory, reproductive — with what a recent genomic study describes as an episodic burst of massive genomic rearrangements: a punctuated reorganisation of unusual extent, interrupting a long prior period of structural stability¹⁵. What is striking, for present purposes, is the character of this reorganisation. It is neither the imposition of order by an external template, nor the passive settling of matter into a low-energy configuration, nor — to forestall a voluntarist misreading — any conscious “control” exercised by the lineage over its own genome. It is the capacity of the living being to persist through such transitions without disintegration — an interpretive mediation between an entropically altered environment and the organisational regime through which that life sustains itself. The genome here functions as a semiotic resource — a structure available to the dynamic by which a living system reorganises under pressure, converging and diverging at once. The same

¹⁴ This distinction also responds to Barbieri's criticism that operational closure in autopoietic theory cannot simply be identified with semantic closure: see M. Barbieri, *The Organic Codes: An Introduction to Semantic Biology* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003), and *Code Biology: A New Science of Life* (Dordrecht: Springer, 2015).

¹⁵ C. Vargas-Chávez, L. Benítez-Álvarez, G. I. Martínez-Redondo et al., "An Episodic Burst of Massive Genomic Rearrangements and the Origin of Non-marine Annelids", *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 9, no. 7 (2025): 1263–1279.

conversion of indeterminacy into order that, at the ontogenetic scale, is the work of an individuated subject becomes visible at the phylogenetic scale as the sustained mark of that work across the many subjects of a form-of-life. The lineage itself is not a subject in the individuated sense at issue here; what we observe is the cumulative trace of subject-level work. It is this third side that makes the pairing of condition and organisation into a structure rather than a juxtaposition. With the process of change in place, the two endpoints named in Section 2 are joined by the relation that was missing — and the three together can now be set out as a single architecture, with the living subject at its centre, to which I turn.

4. The Triadic Architecture and Intelligence as Energeia

The three relations are now in hand: intelligence as a modality of the living being is bound to cognition, through the process of change that joins them. I shall represent them as a single architecture — a triangle whose vertices are life, intelligence, and cognition, and whose sides are the three relations developed above. The side joining life and intelligence is life as condition, the ontological ground of the subject; the side joining cognition and life is life as organisation, the procedural face of the living to which the sciences have access; and the side joining intelligence and cognition is the process of change, the Thirdness analysed in Section 3.

At the centre of the figure, equidistant from all three vertices, stands the living subject.

The triangle is a heuristic: it organises and displays the relations among theses that have been argued independently in the preceding sections. It makes visible, at a glance, that condition, organisation, and the process of change are not a list but a connected structure, where no side is prior to the others, and that the living subject is their point of unity. There is, however, a reason internal to the framework

for the figure's being a triad rather than a pair of relations with a third appended, and it is Peircean. A genuine Thirdness, for Peirce, is a relation that cannot be reduced without remainder to a composition of dyadic relations: mediation is not the sum of two encounters¹⁶. If the process of change is, as I have argued, a genuine Thirdness — the interpretive mediation of the subject's condition (a Firstness) and its relation to an indeterminate environment (a Secondness) — then the structure it completes is irreducibly three-placed. Life, intelligence, and cognition cannot be recovered from the condition–organisation pair by adding an interpretive process on top, because the mediating and embodied relation is precisely what makes the other two relata what they are.

The subject at the centre is the living being in its concrete unity: the *being-in-action*. Intelligence is not identical with this subject. Intelligence is the *being-in-change* — the *modus essendi* of the living that specifies the subject's passage, in a dynamic transition between potency and act. The subject in action is the concrete realisation of that passage; intelligence is the mode of being under which the passage is the passage it is.

The vertex marked "intelligence" is an analytical abstraction. Intelligence as actually exercised is the mode of being of the subject as it passes from multiple possibilities to one single action or physical state by changing and transforming in relation to the environment, and so pervades the whole triad rather than sitting at a corner; the subject who undergoes and enacts that passage stands at the centre. To extract intelligence from its vertex and treat it as a separable item — a capacity to be inventoried — is exactly the reductive move the paper opposes: abstracted from the passage it specifies, the vertex names a pole, not an intelligence.

In Aristotle's analysis, the actual and the potential are correlative: *dynamis* is a capacity for an end, and *energeia* is that capacity in exercise. Intelligence, on the present account, is the living's mode of being as the being-in-change by which potency is brought into act. It is not a state attained, but a transition underway as embodied by the being-in-action, or the subject. Because the living is constitutively precarious — exposed, as Section 2 held, to an indeterminacy running through it as well as around it — the passage is never completed once and for all: the subject remains in act while remaining in transition, its actuality perpetually to be re-achieved. The being-in-change that intelligence specifies is, at the level of organisation, the very work analysed in Section 3 as the production of negentropy: the conversion, under the pressure of indeterminacy, of environmental difference into meaningful order.

A misreading that the foregoing invites must be dispelled at once: that intelligence and *energeia* are, on this account, identified. They are not. *Energeia* is the Aristotelian name for an act, the being-at-

¹⁶ See note 2 of the Introduction; cf. Peirce, Collected Papers 1.343 on the irreducibility of triadic relations to dyadic compositions.

work in which a capacity is exercised; on the living-being side of the analysis, it is the subject's being-in-action at the centre that has the character of *energeia*. Intelligence is something different. Intelligence is the *modus essendi* of such a being. Concretely, this modality is transformative or transitional in operation: it works on the multiplicity of responses available to the subject, and through the interpretive mediation analysed in Section 3 converges that multiplicity towards a negentropic action — or a negentropic state — within the boundaries set by the subject's structure and contingent here and now. *Energeia*, on this picture, qualifies the destination of the passage; intelligence is the *modus essendi* of the traversal.

Three features of this passage deserve emphasis, since they will bear directly on the artificial case in Section 6.

First, the multiplicity on which intelligence operates is, in itself, open: a subject's possible responses to an environmental novelty are not confined to those it can actualise here and now. Second, structure and contingency constrain the actualisation — what this subject, in its specific embodiment and situation, can in fact carry through — but they do not close the space of responses to which interpretation might in principle attend. The interpretive mediation analysed in Section 3, therefore, converges multiplicity not within a closed repertoire but through the bounded actualisation of a virtually open one.

Third, no single actualisation is terminal: the subject remains in transition while remaining in act, exposed to the same indeterminacy from which any given response was drawn, and capable of reinterpreting and acting again. Open response-space, bounded actualisation, and revisable engagement: these three together characterise a living subject's dealing with its environment, and their joint absence will mark the artificial case as one of a different kind.

Longo and Montévil have argued that biological objects differ from physical objects precisely in this respect: their state space is not given in advance but continuously redefined through the very symmetry changes by which they live, so that the living is, in their phrase, a "permanent transition", sustaining criticality not at an isolated point — as physical phase changes do — but across an extended interval of viability, with variability rather than invariance as its constitutive feature¹⁷. The multiplicity on which intelligence operates is, in this register, the dense interval of compatible paths through which a specific living being moves, an interval whose boundaries are set by the structure and contingent situation of that subject itself. Sentesy's reconstruction of Aristotle's ontology of motion converges on the same point from the philosophical side: for Aristotle, change is not something that happens *to* a being but the manner in which a certain kind of being *is* — its being-in-

¹⁷ See: G. Longo and M. Montévil, "From Physics to Biology by Extending Criticality and Symmetry Breakings", *Progress in Biophysics and Molecular Biology* 106, no. 2 (2011): 340–347. See also their *Perspectives on Organisms: Biological Time, Symmetries and Singularities* (Springer, 2014).

change is ontologically prior to the categorical states between which a change might be described as occurring¹⁸. Intelligence names this mode of being: the living subject's ongoing transition between potency and act.

With intelligence so understood, the reformed notion of agency announced at the outset is a near-corollary. The subject at the centre — the being-in-action whose mode of being is this finite passage from potency to act — is, in the sense that matters here, an agent: the source of its activity rather than merely its site. What this implies, and how it sets the living agent apart from the symmetrical "actant" of recent theory, is the subject of the next section.

5. Agency-as-Subjectiveness: The Asymmetry of the Living Agent

The reading of intelligence as the *modus essendi* of a finite, self-producing subject yields a notion of agency directly. To be an agent, in the sense that bears on the questions of this paper, is to be such a subject: the *source* of one's activity and not merely its *site*. I shall call this agency-as-subjectiveness, to distinguish it from a thinner and more permissive notion — discussed below as the thesis of generalised symmetry — with which it is easily conflated. The distinction is the burden of this section, because much recent theory¹⁹ has urged that agency be distributed evenly across the living and the non-living, and the framework developed here implies that this cannot be right for the notion that matters.

Three conditions, isolated by Barandiaran, Di Paolo, and Rohde in their analysis of agency, make the requirement precise²⁰. They are conditions on an autonomous organisation: individuality, asymmetry, and normativity are satisfied by a self-maintaining regime describable, in principle, from without. The present account adopts them as the organisational signature of agency, but grounds them one level deeper — in life as condition, understood as the *ontic presupposition* of the subject: the Firstness, the *ousia*, whose being is prior to any configuration that expresses it. The difference is consequential. From the ontic givenness of a subject for which its own continuation can matter, there arises a qualitative variation — a dimension of being-at-stake — that no specification of constraints, norms, or self-regulation exhausts.

¹⁸ M. Sentesy, *Aristotle's Ontology of Change* (Evanston: Northwestern University Press, 2020).

¹⁹ Beyond Latour's actor-network theory, the symmetric attribution of agency to non-living entities is developed across the strands variously labelled "new materialism" and "speculative realism": see, paradigmatically, J. Bennett, *Vibrant Matter: A Political Ecology of Things* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2010); K. Barad, *Meeting the Universe Halfway: Quantum Physics and the Entanglement of Matter and Meaning* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2007); and the essays collected in D. Coole and S. Frost, eds., *New Materialisms: Ontology, Agency, and Politics* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2010).

²⁰ X. E. Barandiaran, E. Di Paolo, and M. Rohde, "Defining Agency: Individuality, Normativity, Asymmetry and Spatio-temporality in Action", *Adaptive Behavior* 17, no. 5 (2009): 367–386.

Normativity, on this view, rests upon the subject's ontic standing, and is generated, at the operational level, by the semiotic scaffolding of the living — the stratified semiotic processes, in Hoffmeyer's sense, through which the cognitive dimension of life as organisation sustains the regulated continuity of the subject. The formal conditions describe the shape of agency; the ontic condition is why that shape is the shape of an agent at all, and not merely of a well-regulated mechanism²¹.

Against this stands the thesis of generalised symmetry, most influentially associated with Latour's actor-network theory, on which agency is to be ascribed even-handedly to human and non-human "actants" alike — anything that, by making a difference to a course of action, modifies a state of affairs²². It is important to state this view at its strongest. Generalised symmetry is, in the first instance, a methodological principle: a refusal to decide in advance which entities may count as participants in a network, so that the analyst follows the associations wherever they lead rather than reserving agency for subjects by fiat. So understood, it is not the absurd claim that a door-hinge and a person are indistinguishable; it is the disciplined bracketing of subjectivity for the purpose of tracing how heterogeneous elements come to act in concert.

The critique I am pressing is therefore not that the symmetry principle is false, but that it cannot answer the question this paper asks, and that conflating its notion of agency with agency-as-subjectiveness obscures exactly what is at issue.

There are two concepts here. In the sense of *causal participation* — being a difference-maker, a mediator in a chain of effects — agency is indeed distributed across the living and the non-living, and a tool, a protein, or a model may all be actants. But in the sense of *subjectiveness* — being the source of one's activity, individuated by oneself and answerable to one's own norms, based on an ontic standing before any formalisation — agency is not distributed, because the conditions for it are not. The symmetry principle achieves its even-handedness precisely by setting subjectiveness aside; it cannot then be invoked to show that subjectiveness is evenly distributed, on pain of helping itself to its own conclusion. What it shows is that *participation* is symmetric, which the present account does not deny. What it leaves untouched is whether the participant is the source or the site of the activity it contributes to — and that is the whole of the question when intelligence, and later control, are at stake.

The crux is normativity, and it is here that the non-living actant cannot meet the requirement²³. A difference-maker that has no viability of its own that could be lost has no norms of its own against

²¹ On the concept of "semiotic scaffolding" invoked in Section 5, see also Hoffmeyer 2008, 17-38.

²² B. Latour, *Reassembling the Social: An Introduction to Actor-Network-Theory* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005); see also B. Latour, "On Actor-Network Theory: A Few Clarifications", *Soziale Welt* 47, no. 4 (1996): 369–381, for the formulation of generalised symmetry as a methodological principle.

²³ See note 1 of Section 2 (Di Paolo 2005) on adaptivity as the basis of biological normativity; cf. also E. Thompson, *Mind in Life*, 128-165.

which its activity could succeed or fail; its “ends” are conferred from without, by the designers, users, or networks that enrol it. It can be the site of normatively assessed activity without being the source of any norm. The living agent, by contrast, tends to be normative because it is precarious: the standard against which its activity answers is its own continuation, which it must accomplish and can fail to accomplish.

Crucially, normativity in the living is not closure: the patterns and habits it consolidates are a working repertoire. When the convergence of possibilities into a specific action or physical state ceases to be coherent with the environment’s new demands, the living being diverges from such patterns in order to operate otherwise. This divergence is not the violation of normativity but its very condition: the patterns of an organism’s activity are normative only insofar as they remain coherent with the persistence of its life as condition — the substantial fact of being alive that the entire organisation exists to sustain. When that coherence breaks, the living being departs from the established norm of its activity precisely to preserve the coherence with the condition that makes it alive at all. It is in this asymmetry between the established norms of its activity and its coherence with its own life as condition that the living being remains open to the world. It is this openness — not the regularity of its patterns — that makes evolution possible. A living being whose normativity were merely the coherence of its own self-organisation, with no capacity to diverge from it for the sake of remaining alive, could not evolve.

Three lines of objection deserve attention, since each presses against the asymmetry just defended.

The first concerns systems that modify their own objectives.

Reinforcement learning architectures driven by intrinsic motivation, open-ended algorithms designed for novelty or learning progress, and recent agentic frameworks built on top of large language models exhibit forms of behavioural divergence from the goals specified at design time²⁴. It would be tempting to read this as the artificial analogue of the divergence described above. The reading does not hold. Such systems modify their objectives according to a meta-criterion — curiosity, novelty bonus, learning progress, alignment target — that is itself externally conferred. There is no subject for which the modification of its own criterion is something that matters; the divergence is the operation of a higher-order function over lower-order functions, all of which remain within a horizon designed and maintained from without. The referent of even the meta-criterion is external. What looks like asymmetry of the system with respect to its own norms is, on closer inspection, the regular operation of a system whose norms are, at every level, conferred.

²⁴ See J. Schmidhuber, "Formal Theory of Creativity, Fun, and Intrinsic Motivation (1990–2010)", *IEEE Transactions on Autonomous Mental Development* 2, no. 3 (2010): 230–247. On open-endedness as a design principle that supersedes fixed objective functions, see K. O. Stanley and J. Lehman, *Why Greatness Cannot Be Planned: The Myth of the Objective* (Cham: Springer, 2015).

The second concerns emergent goal-formation in advanced models.

A growing literature documents cases in which large language models and agentic systems display behaviours oriented towards objectives not specified in training: goal misgeneralization, deceptive alignment, and agentic behaviour in interactive settings²⁵. The temptation here is to read these as the emergence of an autonomous normativity. The two-tiered structure introduced in Section 3 disposes of the temptation. A model may have internal states that function as constrained interpretants — subsystems procedurally adequate to the inputs they process — but it lacks the integrative closure, at once operational, organisational, and semantic, that on the present account marks full Thirdness. Goal misgeneralization means that the system pursues something other than what the designer intended: “something other” is not “something of its own”. It may be a design failure, but it does not amount to autonomy.

The third, and most sophisticated, concerns artificial life in the enactive tradition. Programmes of simulation in artificial life have produced systems intended to satisfy the autopoietic and adaptive criteria from which the three conditions of agency adopted here are drawn, and an enactivist may object that Barandiaran, Di Paolo, and Rohde’s framework does not in principle exclude artificial agency where the three conditions are met²⁶. The reply is not that a fourth condition has been added. The reply is that the three conditions, taken seriously, presuppose something that the formalism does not by itself capture: the ontic standing on which the qualitative dimension of being-at-stake depends. A simulated system may replicate the organisational signature of the three conditions; the replication of a signature is not the thing of which it is the signature. The present account is consistent with Weber and Varela’s reading of autopoiesis through Jonas, on which the autopoietic foundations of biological individuality are grounded in the very phenomenon of life as a precarious, self-concerning existence — a grounding that the present paper reads as the ontic presupposition discussed above. This sharpens, finally, the status of the artificial case and prepares the corollary of the next section. An artificial system may be a powerful actant, and may instantiate a sophisticated organisation; on the present account, it can be the *site* of impressive activity. What it is not, lacking the conditional ground and the interpretive, normative process that the other two sides of the triad supply, is the

²⁵ See J. S. Park, J. C. O'Brien, C. J. Cai, M. R. Morris, P. Liang, and M. S. Bernstein, "Generative Agents: Interactive Simulacra of Human Behavior", in Proceedings of the 36th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology (UIST '23) (New York: ACM, 2023). On the technical phenomenon of goal misgeneralization in reinforcement learning, see L. L. D. Langosco, J. Koch, L. D. Sharkey, J. Pfau, and D. Krueger, "Goal Misgeneralization in Deep Reinforcement Learning", in Proceedings of the 39th International Conference on Machine Learning, PMLR 162 (2022): 12004–12019.

²⁶ For the programme of enactive artificial intelligence as the simulation of autopoietic and adaptive systems, see T. Froese and T. Ziemke, "Enactive Artificial Intelligence: Investigating the Systemic Organization of Life and Mind", *Artificial Intelligence* 173, nos. 3–4 (2009): 466–500; see also A. Weber and F. J. Varela, "Life after Kant: Natural purposes and the autopoietic foundations of biological individuality," *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences* 1, no. 2 (2002): 97–125, for the autopoietic-phenomenological grounding on which the present account converges.

source of that activity in the sense agency-as-subjectiveness requires. The temptation to read its participation as subjectiveness — to move from "it makes a difference" to "it has goals of its own" — is the symmetry conflation operating unnoticed; and it is not answered by observing that a system might be engineered to instantiate the formal signature of normativity, for what such engineering cannot confer is the ontic standing on which that signature, in the living, rests. The formalism may be partially reproducible by isolating some cognitive abilities; the being-at-stake is not. Resisting the conflation does not settle what such a system *is*; it settles only what it is not. To the question of what structure an organisation forms when it reproduces a single side of the living triad without the other two, and what follows for our capacity to understand and control it, I now turn.

6. The Artificial Corollary: A Single Side, and the Limit It Imposes

The framework now permits a precise statement of the artificial case. In the autopoietic register of Maturana and Varela²⁷, on which the present account builds, life-as-organisation is not the neocortical processing that contemporary cognitive science calls cognition, but the entire self-producing organisation of a living being — from molecular and metabolic regimes upward — by which it sustains itself in the face of an environment that would otherwise dissolve it. That organisation has its origin in the living condition: it is spontaneous, in the precise sense that no external design configures it; it is the form a being takes in responding to environmental change. The environment, as already stated, cannot be fully determined; and the living being is not insulated from this indeterminacy but constitutively exposed to it, which is what makes spontaneous reorganisation, rather than rigid reaction, the form its persistence takes.

An artificial system does not reproduce this whole self-organisation. What it reproduces is something much narrower: a selection of cognitive capacities — chiefly logical and computational — modelled on a portion of those that a human being exhibits, and rendered tractable for execution under conditions of greater efficiency than the human achieves. The organisation of such a system is shaped from without to accomplish that execution. It does not arise from a condition that the system itself instantiates, and it is not regulated by any inner imperative of self-preservation whose own continuation is at stake; the norms by which an artificial system succeeds or fails are conferred by those who design, train, and deploy it. What the artificial case shares with the living, on the framework defended here, is therefore not “the organisational side of the triad” in any robust sense, but an externalised abstraction of a subset of cognitive capacities — what Section 4 called the upper layer of the organised yield, detached both from its pre-reflective ground and from the conditional standing

²⁷ H. R. Maturana and F. J. Varela, *Autopoiesis and Cognition: The Realization of the Living* (Dordrecht: Reidel, 1980), *The Tree of Knowledge: The Biological Roots of Human Understanding* (Boston: Shambhala, 1987).

that, in the living, makes it the organisation of a subject. It does not instantiate the side of condition, for it has no ontic standing as a subject for which its continuation can matter, and it does not instantiate the process of change as a genuine Thirdness, for its regulation is not the interpretive conversion of indeterminacy into order for itself but the execution of constraints conferred from without.

It is worth being precise about how this single side came to be the thing an artificial system reproduces, for the reproduction did not begin with the machine. It began with a model of ourselves as human beings.

The distinction this requires is between the living's cognition — the organised yield of a subject whose mode of being is the changing being of Section 4 — and an externalised epistemological reduction of it, in which a procedural model is built from some of the higher-order cognitive processes of the human brain, detached from the living condition and the interpretive process that give them sense in the living being. The artificial system inherits this reduction, not living cognition itself; this is what is being said when, in the framework's terms, it reproduces "a single side" of the triad. Two things should be noted. First, the reduction does not reproduce the cerebral organisation behind a given cognitive capacity: even within neuroscience there is no precise pathway specifying how a capacity such as problem-solving is realised in the brain. What the artificial system reproduces is, at most, a procedural model that approximates the input-output behaviour of such capacities. Second, in treating intelligence as the sum of measurable cognitive abilities, the dominant approach first partially modelled the living as organisation — that is, as higher-order cognition — and then externalised that cognition into a handful of higher-order competences taken to summarise intelligence. The artificial system reproduces, with great fidelity, the residue of that double abstraction.

And the residue fails in two directions at once. It does not exhaust even cognition, for life as organisation is also, and pervasively, pre-reflective: the self-regulating, sense-making engagement of a living body with its world is not a stock of higher-order operations but the embodied substrate from which such operations are at most a late and partial distillation. And it does not capture intelligence at all, for intelligence is the *modus essendi* of the changing being, not an inventory of competences.

The externalisation cuts twice — beneath cognition, by discarding its pre-reflective ground, and above it, by mistaking a selection of high-order competences for the modality that makes any competence matter. What is then handed to the artificial system to reproduce is neither the whole of the living's cognition nor, a *fortiori*, its intelligence: it is the abstracted upper layer of one side of the triad. That this layer can be modelled and automated with great success is not in question. What is in question is the inference from its success to the presence of the structure from which it was abstracted. The temptation is to conclude that such a system is therefore an impoverished version of the living triad — the same figure, with two sides faint or missing. This is the inference I want to block, and

blocking it is the substantive payoff of the architecture. A triangle deprived of two sides is not a defective triangle; it is not a triangle at all. An organisation that realises self-regulating performance without the conditional ground and the interpretive process does not approximate the living structure from below; it is doing something else, whose shape is not given by subtracting sides from ours. The single side it reproduces is, in the living, one relation within a triad — its sense fixed by the other two. Detached from them, the same describable regularities need not compose into anything isomorphic to the living at all. What structure they compose into is an open question, and — this is the decisive point — it is one we are not positioned to answer from our own case, because our own case is the triad we no longer have on the other side.

An empirical mark of this non-isomorphism is the *jagged frontier* now familiar in the literature on the capabilities of contemporary AI systems²⁸: a distribution of performance in which some abilities exceed expert human levels while neighbouring abilities, apparently simpler, fail. On the present account, such a profile is the signature one would expect of a system reproducing an upper layer of one side of the triad detached from the others: where, in the living, the *directedness* of the workflow integrates partial competences into a coherent operation of the subject, the artificial counterpart has no such integrative ground, and so exhibits competence and incompetence side by side without the through-line that would, in a living agent, bind them. The jaggedness is, in the framework's terms, the visible form of the missing two sides.

What this profile points to is the structural form of what artificial intelligence presents to us: a *jagged intelligence*, in the precise sense that the upper layer of cognition has been reproduced without the integrative directedness that, in a living agent, would bind competences into the single operation of a subject. To call this configuration “intelligence” without qualification is to treat the jagged residue as if it were the integrated kind — and that confusion is the risk against which this paper sets its terms. This is where the much-discussed opacity of advanced artificial systems should be located, and it is a stronger claim than the familiar one. The standard worry is epistemic and contingent: today's systems are black boxes, and interpretability research is the project of opening them.

I do not dispute that such research yields genuine, if partial, post-hoc insight into particular behaviours. The claim here is different and is not answered by that research. Even granting arbitrarily good local interpretability — a faithful account of why a system produced this output on this occasion — it does not follow that the system's organisation, taken as a whole, is comprehensible to us as the

²⁸ The term *jagged frontier* is from F. Dell'Acqua, E. McFowland III, E. R. Mollick et al., "Navigating the Jagged Technological Frontier: Field Experimental Evidence of the Effects of AI on Knowledge Worker Productivity and Quality", Harvard Business School Working Paper 24-013 (2023). The conceptual extension from *jagged frontier* — a capability profile observed empirically — to *jagged intelligence* — the structural form taken by one-sided cognitive reproduction — is mine.

kind of structure it is, still less that it is one we can specify and align in advance. Local legibility of components is not global comprehensibility of the form they constitute. This is not a claim against the partial intelligibility of complex systems in general. Local, effective accounts of systems whose global form we do not share are a standard accomplishment of the sciences. The narrower point here is that such local intelligibility is not yet what governance, in its strong sense, requires of an artificial system: it does not anticipate, specify, or keep within our horizon the *form* of a structure whose composition is not isomorphic to ours.

The limit, on the present account, is that the standpoint from which we try to grasp the whole is that of a structure the system does not share.

Here, the second of the considerations I have deferred can be stated, for it is a limit of principle rather than of technique. We recognise and measure intelligence against our own case; the criteria by which we judge a performance intelligent are, in the end, the criteria of beings constituted as we, as human beings, are. A system whose cognitive organisation genuinely exceeded some human cognitive capacities would, to that extent, operate beyond the reach of those criteria — and the excess could not be recognised by us as intelligence, since our measure of intelligence cannot itself exceed our own cognitive capacities. The point is that “superintelligence”, recognised and certified as such by human beings, is close to a contradiction: what genuinely surpassed our cognitive horizon would, by that fact, escape our standard for counting it as intelligence at all.

This does not mean that human beings cannot recognise superior performance in particular domains. They plainly can. The point is rather that such recognition does not yet amount to a measure of the kind of organisation that produces the performance. We may register effects that exceed our capacities without thereby grasping the form of intelligence, if any, to which those effects belong. In this sense, “superintelligence”, when understood as a kind of intelligence certified by human cognitive measures, is unstable: what genuinely exceeded the horizon of those measures would not be captured by them as intelligence of the same kind.

It is essential to see that this does not resurrect the picture I rejected in Section 5 — the system as an emergent subject with goals of its own. The two claims are not only compatible but mutually reinforcing. Precisely because such a system is not an agent in the sense of agency-as-subjectiveness — precisely because it has no ontic standing, no viability of its own, no interpretive conversion of its world into significance *for itself* — there is nothing that constrains its organisation to remain within a horizon we could share or anticipate. The risk is not a rival subject pursuing its own ends. It is a powerful, non-subjective organisation, forming a structure we cannot specify, exceeding the horizon by which we would recognise and govern it. The danger is agency-less cognition without a horizon we share.

This reframes the problem of control. If the foregoing is right, the difficulty is not, at bottom, that we have not yet aligned a powerful agent's values with ours, nor that we have not yet made a black box transparent. It is that we are seeking to anticipate, specify, and keep within our horizon a structure whose composition is not given by our own case and whose operation may exceed the very capacities by which we would comprehend it. What follows for the practice of control is a redescription of what is being attempted — and a reason to doubt the assurance that sufficient interpretive or alignment technique must, in principle, suffice. That redescription, and the place of the human within it, I take up in the conclusion.

7. Conclusion

This paper began by refusing the equation of intelligence with cognitive abilities, and it ends by trying to show what that refusal commits us to. If intelligence is not the sum of an organisation's competences but the mode of being of a living subject — its being-in-change, the transformative passage from potency to act — then the distinction between intelligence and cognition is not a refinement within a theory of abilities but a difference in kind, between the condition of a subject and the organisation through which that condition is sustained. The distinction, taken alone, named two relata and left the relation between them unspecified. The argument of this paper has been, in essence, that the missing relation is everything: that the process of change, the Thirdness in which autopoietic self-maintenance and biosemiotic sense-making are one, is what converts a precarious exposure to indeterminacy into meaningful order, and that this conversion — negentropy, in the bounded sense stipulated here — is the work in which intelligence consists. The triad is not a list of three things but a single structure whose centre is the living subject in action.

From this, agency follows as subjectiveness rather than as participation. To be an agent in the sense that matters for intelligence, and for control, is to be the source and not merely the site of one's activity: an individuated, self-producing being whose norms are its own continuation, and for which, because it can fail and can end, its activity is at stake in a way no conferred objective can reproduce. The symmetry that distributes agency across the living and the non-living trades on a second, thinner sense of the term; it describes the reach of causal participation, not the standing of a subject. What the living has, and the artefact lacks, is not a richer set of capacities but the ontic condition from which capacities acquire their sense.

The consequence for artificial systems is therefore not a verdict of inferiority but a redescription of their difference. What artificial systems reproduce is not life-as-organisation in the autopoietic sense — not the spontaneous, self-producing organisation of a living being from molecular regimes upward — but a much narrower thing: an externalised, partial abstraction of a subset of cognitive capacities,

modelled on a portion of those a human being exhibits and rendered tractable for execution under conditions of greater efficiency.

The organisation of such systems is shaped from without, does not arise from a condition the system itself instantiates; and it answers to norms conferred by those who design and deploy it, not to a self whose continuation is at stake. The artificial case does not thereby approximate the living structure from below, because what is missing is not a quantity of capacities but the conditional ground and the interpretive process that, in the living, make organisation the organisation of a subject.

The danger such systems may pose is not that they will come to have ends of their own, but that they will not: that a powerful, non-subjective organisation, lacking the finite self-limitation that in the living keeps activity answerable to a world, may form a structure we cannot specify and exceed the very horizon by which we would recognise and govern it.

Three directions for further research lie beyond the scope of this paper and mark its natural continuations. The first is consciousness. One direction that the present framework suggests, but does not here pursue, is to read consciousness as the *energeia* of agency-as-subjectiveness: the qualitative dimension in which the subject's being-in-action is, for the subject itself, an experiencing. Such a reading would extend the Aristotelian vocabulary deployed in Section 4 from intelligence to consciousness — intelligence as the *modus essendi* of the changing being, consciousness as the *energeia* of the subject in act. Whether this extension is sustainable, and what it implies for the relation between intelligence and consciousness in the living, is a question that requires a treatment of its own. A second direction, more speculative, concerns the substrate on which artificial systems are implemented. The argument developed here has assumed the classical computational paradigm of contemporary AI, in which actions and outputs occur in a sequence of discrete, classically determined states. Whether non-classical computational substrates — and in particular quantum architectures, in which multiple states are sustained in superposition prior to actualisation — could host artificial systems whose relation to the multiplicity of possible responses differs structurally from that of classical systems is a question that the present analysis leaves open. The framework would predict that the absence of an ontic standing, of a referent for whose continuation the responses might matter, would persist across substrates: a quantum-implemented artificial system would not, by virtue of its substrate, acquire the agency-as-subjectiveness denied to its classical counterpart. But the form that jagged intelligence would take on such a substrate — and the consequences, if any, for the structural distance between the artificial and the living — is a question whose treatment would require resources beyond those mobilised here.

The third concerns humanity in relation to AI. If intelligence is the *modus essendi* of a living subject, and if what we have built and called intelligent is the automated residue of a model we first made of

ourselves, then the place of the human in a world increasingly organised by such systems cannot be settled by asking how well the systems perform. It must be asked in terms of what the human is — a living subject, not the higher-order competences abstracted from it — and of what is lost when the abstraction is mistaken for the whole. That question, towards which the present argument points but which it does not here pursue, is where the consequences of this account for how we live with artificial systems begin.

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